

Quota-Based Measured Fishing for the Sustainability of Fishery Resources in Indonesia

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Abstract: Measured Fishing (PIT) is one of the government's efforts to preserve fish resources while optimizing economic and social benefits for fishermen and fisheries business actors. PIT is implemented through setting catch quota limits (catch limits) as output control and is the first fisheries management model implemented in Indonesia. This model is an alternative to the policy of limiting ship permits (input control) which has so far been considered to be less implementable, creates a 'race to fish' mentality, and is prone to manipulation of ship size (markdown). The PNB contribution to the capture fisheries sector is currently dominated by Pre-production Fishery Product Levy (PHP) which is withdrawn from Business Licensing based on the Vessel Tonnage (GT) variable and the benchmark fish price. This policy is considered unfair and does not provide business certainty for fisheries business actors because the levy is collected before the fishing effort begins, even though there is a risk of business activity failure. The pre-production PNB system also has the potential to worsen the stock status of fish resources because business actors maximize catches to gain as much profit as possible (race-to-fish). Through the quota-based PIT policy, the number of catches will be limited for each vessel according to the zone. PIT minimizes manipulation of vessel size, maximizes state income through PNB, fulfills the principle of business justice because levies are taken after fishing efforts are carried out based on the size of the catch, and maintains the active participation of small fishermen in accordance with the quota given to the regions. Through the implementation of this policy, improving the welfare of Indonesian fishermen, balancing economic activities across regions, sustainability of fisheries resources and marine health can be achieved.

Keywords: measurable fishing, economic benefits, sustainability, resource.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has the potential for rich fish resources of up to 12 million tons per year, as stipulated in the Decree of the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries No. 19 of 2022. Indonesian capture fisheries production continues to increase from year to year along with the increasing number of fishing fleets operating in eleven Fisheries Management Area (WPPNRI). Capture fisheries in the archipelago are unique because they have different characteristics from fisheries in other parts of the world. Indonesian waters are not only rich in types of fish (multi species) but also have various types of fishing gear (multi fishing gear). As a tropical marine area, Indonesian marine waters have various types of economically important fish, but the number and abundance of each type of fish is relatively small.

Fishing activities in Indonesia are still dominated by small scale fisheries, while industrial scale fisheries are distributed unevenly in Fisheries Management Areas (WPPNRI). For example, WPP 712 (Java Sea) and WPP 718 (Arafura Sea) are the densest fishing areas in Indonesia, with a fleet of vessels with central permits (> 30 GT) having reached a total of more than 2300 actively licensed fishing vessels. On the other hand, several WPPs such as WPP 717 (North Pacific Ocean of Papua) and WPP 716 (Sulawesi Sea) only have dozens of active licensed fishing vessels. The fishing gear and fish resources caught are also varied and different in each WPP. The Arafura Sea is a fishing area for demersal, shrimp, squid and large pelagic fish groups where bottom longline fishing gear, squid fishing rods and drift gill nets dominate, while fishing vessels in the waters of the Java Sea (WPP 712) are dominated by bagged drag nets. targeting bottom fish, squid and small pelagics.

The uneven distribution of the fishing vessel fleet between WPPNRI and the use of diverse fishing gear is a manifestation of adjustments to targets for the type of fish caught and existing regulation models. The amount of Non-Tax State Revenue (PNBP) originating from ship permits is very dependent on the number and size of ships, resulting in fishing ships getting bigger and increasing in number, because entrepreneurs can maximize profits from large ships and a larger number of ships. The more and bigger the ships, the more profits you will get. On the other hand, regulations at the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (KKP) do not clearly regulate the number and allocation of vessels at each WPP, although the National Commission for the Study of Fish Resources (Komnaskajiskan) has determined the stock status and level of utilization of fish resources at each WPPNRI. The regulations in force so far only regulate the spatial area of fishing, but the catch limit per each vessel and the permitted allocation of vessels per WPPNRI have not been properly regulated. To maintain resource sustainability, as well as optimize the economic benefits of the fisheries sector, the Indonesian government through the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries is currently working to realize a quota and zone-based Measured Fishing (PIT) program. The meaning of measurable is defined as under control, an antonym of out of control or uncontrollable. Thus, quota-based PIT is defined as controlled capture fisheries management, based on output control where the number of fish caught must not exceed the permitted catch. Each ship is given a portion of the catch quota, then the actual number of catches must be reported to ensure that each ship catches fish does not exceed the quota given.

The quota-based fisheries management model has been proven by vessel size, and fishing gear). This study proves that the catch limit model can support the sustainability of fish resources. However, on the other hand, limiting effort (number of vessels and fishing gear) will only increase fishing intensity in fisheries that are not yet well regulated. For example, restrictions on the number and size of ships actually have the potential to increase the number of crew members at sea and encourage fishermen to increase the number and power of ship engines to maximize catches. This will ultimately threaten the sustainability of fish resources. A study conducted by Kasim (2019) regarding the cantrang fishery in the Java Sea also shows that after the cantrang ban, fishermen tended to extend fishing trips and increase the number of crew members (ABK) per boat in order to be able to catch as many fish as possible. Hoshino et al. (2020) also stated that quota-based fisheries management (individual transferable catch quota, ITQ) has been proven to provide economic incentives for fishermen and fisheries business actors, and makes it easier to adjust fisheries activities based on changes in biological and economic condition factors of resources without involving efforts to reduce the amount of effort. (fleet of ships) which means by the government.

Currently the number of Indonesian capture fisheries fleet continues to grow and operates in 11 Fisheries Management Areas (WPP). Several WPPs such as WPP 712 (Java Sea), WPP 718 (Arafura Sea), WPP 711 (Karimata Strait and Natuna Sea), and WPP 572 (South Java) are the main fishing areas with fishing fleet permits reaching more than 70% of the total allocation. in

Indonesia. The threat of overfishing in several WPPs which are the main fishing areas is increasingly worrying and causing a shortage of fish resources that can be caught (Wati et al., 2014). The results of a study by the National Commission for the Study of Fish Stocks (Konnaskajiskan) through Ministerial Decree No. 19 of 2022 show that the level of utilization of large pelagics and demersal in WPP 712 (Java Sea) has respectively reached 130% and 110% of the total allowable catch (JTB). Indicators of overfishing include the total production of fish caught being greater than the Maximum Sustainable Yield, fish catches decreasing, the size of fish caught decreasing, and fishing grounds becoming farther from the coast so that fishing becomes more difficult. If this situation is allowed to continue, it will greatly affect the survival of fishermen in the area (Nugroho & Dahuri, 2012).

Hilborn et al. (2020) also said that management of fish resources is open access (open use) and minimal management, that is, everyone can use fisheries resources with a lack of control over the number of fleets or restrictions on the number of catches, which has the potential to create overfishing. However, fisheries areas that are managed using a scientific management approach (scientific-based management) are able to increase the abundance of fish resources. PIT will organize and re-manage national fisheries through rational and scientific management of fish resources. Monitoring, Controlling and Surveillance Systems (MCS) are needed to support the formation of effective and accurate information systems and influence fish resource management planning that ensures sustainable fishing (Ernawati & Zuliyati, 2018).

The integrity of coastal ecosystems is very important for marine health, so global warming, excessive and unsustainable economic activities and coastal exploitation must be addressed. By improving the welfare of coastal communities by increasing income through fishing quotas, it is hoped that coastal areas will remain protected. Based on the explanation above, the aim of this research is to convey the concept of quota-based measurable fishing to improve the fishermen's economy and protect the environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article was written based on the results of a literature review (review) from various sources such as national and international scientific journals, national and international seminar proceedings and other library sources. Various relevant library sources obtained from internet access, libraries, related agencies are collected and compiled according to the subjects that have been prepared in the form of a framework.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION THE URGENCY OF MEASURED FISHING

In principle, fishing activities will continue if each fishing business unit still earns business profits. The number of vessels will continue to increase (vessel entry) into waters until they reach a balance point where each individual fishing vessel no longer produces business profit (zero profit). Anderson, et.al. (2018) stated that in open access fisheries (open access, namely fisheries without limits on the number of vessels and the number of catches), the number of new fishermen (new entry vessels) will tend to increase while existing fishermen will try as much as possible to increase investment by increasing the size of their vessels, as well as fishing capacity so that the catch is maximum. As a result, investment flows for fishing businesses are increasing, but net profits from fishing businesses are getting smaller for each vessel due to increasingly tight competition and deteriorating fish resource stocks. Fishing activities will stop when there are no more incentives for business actors (zero profit), and there are businesses (other jobs) that are more profitable. Without regulation, fishing will continue as long as it still produces a small profit, even though fish stocks are deteriorating. In many cases of world fisheries, very high fishing pressure which exceeds the ability to recover resources has resulted in the depletion of fish resource stocks which is known as the biological tragedy of the common.

Measured Fishing is a fishing policy based on quotas (catch limits) and zones, where the number of catches and fishing zones are limited. This policy is one of the important steps taken by the government to change national fisheries governance so that fish stocks are maintained and provide optimal economic benefits for fishermen and fisheries business actors. Limitations on the regulation of fishing activities include the number of vessels, number of catches, regulation of the type of fish caught, regulation of fishing equipment (API), fishing time, and suitability of the landing port (fish landing at the port where the catch quota is issued) (Figure 1). A measurable fishing policy certainly has its own benefits and impacts on coastal areas. The benefits that can be obtained from this program include: 1) Maintaining fish availability and marine health; 2) the entrepreneur's ability to determine optimal vessel allocation to maximize profits; 3) Achieving regional economic equality and growth (ports adapt to fishing areas); 4) Accuracy of data collection; 5) Optimization of industry at the landing port. 6) High PNB income.

The externality of metered fishing is a limitation on the amount of costs operational and optimum profit for the given quota. Measurable fishing also has a main objective which is expected to have a positive impact in its implementation. The main objectives include: 1) Creating a socially just fishing business where regional fishermen also receive quotas in zones according to their allocation, thereby encouraging an increase in the welfare of small fishermen; 2) Sustainable use of fish resources and preventing overfishing; 3) Increasing the profitability of the capture fisheries sector which can be seen as increasing the contribution of fishing business actors to the regional and national economy (PNBP-GDP), which ultimately stimulates regional economic growth. Apart from that, PIT is also expected to be able to have a multiplier effect, including opening up employment opportunities, developing the fishing industry in fish landing areas that comply with permits (the fisheries industry includes fish processing, shipyards, ice factories, cold storage, etc.), developing logistics services, easier traceability of fishery products, improved credibility of the fisheries sector towards the banking industry, as well as stimulus for the tourism industry.

In general, pond areas in Central Sulawesi are owned by the people and are managed traditionally with a single water supply and output system due to the lack of adequate irrigation channels. The low tidal fluctuations in Tomini Bay mean that many ponds require pumps. The dominant types of brackish water cultivation commodities cultivated by local farmers are tiger prawns, vaname and milkfish. Meanwhile, seawater cultivation commodities are dominated by seaweed and grouper (DKPD Central Sulawesi Province, 2009).

The mainstay aquaculture commodity in Central Sulawesi Province is seaweed, with the amount of production fluctuating since 2013 and experiencing a decline in production to only 900 thousand tons in 2017. This decline in production is generally caused by attacks by "ice-ice" and fish diseases. seaweed predators, repeated use of seaweed seeds which causes slow growth, lack of accurate information regarding the correct planting season and the network of facilities and infrastructure that support the cultivation and marketing process. Increasing seaweed production in Tomini Bay is still very possible provided the above problems can be overcome. This is because the potential for cultivation areas in Tomini Bay is very large. For example, the potential for seaweed cultivation, *Kappaphycus alvarezii* in Parigi Moutong Regency, Central Sulawesi Province, reaches 62 thousand hectares. If it is assumed that the maximum land use is 2% of the total available land (6.2 thousand hectares) and the minimum total production is 500 tons/hectare, then Parigi Moutong Regency can produce 0.62 million wet tons of seaweed or around 70% of the total seaweed production in Central Sulawesi.

Production of commodities other than seaweed shows an increasing trend every year. This shows that mariculture in Tomini Bay also has great potential for development. One example is the level of live grouper shipping traffic which tends to increase in WPPNRI 715 for Gorontalo Province from 2009 by 26 thousand tons to 49 thousand tons in 2016 (Ahmad et al.,

2017). Although this data does not separate the results of cultivation and capture fisheries, the relatively large marketing volume of grouper fish shows great potential for development of cultivation related to optimal habitat for grouper growth.

Another area in Tomini Bay that has potential for cultivation development is the Togean Islands located in Central Sulawesi. The sea waters of this archipelago have been identified as having available land for marine cultivation of Floating Net Cages (KJA) of 1000 hectares which can accommodate 4000 KJA units measuring²2.5 to 2.5 m (Utojo et al., 2007).

FISHING CONTROL

Some of the key points in Ministerial Regulation KP 18/2021 are the regulation of prohibited fishing gear (API), such as the group of drift nets consisting of bottom trawls, bottom prawn trawls, slatted bottom trawls, double-barred trolley trawls, double-height trawls. ships, and fishing trawlers.

To implement the concept of measured fishing, including the implementation of Ministerial Decree KP 18/2021, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries can maximize monitoring efforts, which include strengthening patrol teams, fleets and the role of technology in cracking down on violations. Currently, the KKP has dozens of surveillance vessels, aerial surveillance aircraft and a surveillance center that is capable of monitoring the movements of fishing vessels through the Vessel Monitoring System (VMS). There are 3 monitoring schemes carried out, including before going to sea, during sea and after going to sea. For example, after going to sea, an inspection is carried out to validate the catch using the fishing gear used. Strict action will be taken against violators because the use of fishing gear that is not permitted causes social conflict and threatens the sustainability of the ecosystem.

The implementation of PIT is carried out through reform of the governance of the capture fisheries subsector throughout Indonesia's marine waters. Apart from having a positive impact on fisheries business activities, this policy will also broadly maintain the health of the sea and coastal ecosystems (Directorate General of Marine Spatial Management, 2022). Allocation of the optimum number of vessels in each zone encourages the use of fuel efficiency for fishing vessels, which ultimately plays a role in controlling emissions that cause greenhouse gas effects. As is known, the sea plays an important role in the process of absorbing and storing carbon and is able to store more carbon reserves than forest ecosystems on land. The possibility of fishing violations occurring in conservation zones or areas is also expected to decrease with the implementation of quota-based PIT.

Optimizing potential state revenues through PNBPN can only be achieved with policy support that balances economic and conservation interests. And still maintain social benefits. This balance is stimulated by a measured fishing policy accompanied by firm law enforcement efforts in all zones or eleven State Fisheries Management Areas of the Republic of Indonesia (WPP NRI). So that law enforcement runs smoothly, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (KKP) focuses on preparing a legal umbrella that regulates measured fishing activities. Thus, all related activities can be carried out in accordance with applicable regulations. The advantages of a strong legal umbrella include guaranteeing certainty of business for perpetrators of the arrest business, ensuring the facilities and infrastructure needed for law enforcement. Through firm and appropriate legal action, Indonesia's reputation before the international community will gradually improve in the future, especially towards member countries of the High Level Panel on Sustainable Ocean Economy (HLP SOE).

High potential associatedThe availability of land for marine cultivation, both for seaweed and for economical marine cultivated fish in WPPNRI 715 Tomini Bay, has implications for several things related to the use of marine space and management of fish resources:

CONCLUSION

This measured fishing policy will be able to improve the fishermen's economy while still maintaining optimum vessels to obtain maximum profits; happen regional economic equality (landing ports are adjusted to fishing areas); accuracy of capture data; industrial optimization at the landing port; building certainty of investment returns in the long term; and high PNPB receipts.

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